

Flux and Quantum One Dimensional Reflection-Refraction

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In the case of one dimensional photon reflection-refraction, one may write a simple, static probability statement: $1 = \text{Probability}(\text{reflect}) + \text{Probability}(\text{refract})$ ((1)). The problem, however, is a dynamic one and if many photons are in the incident beam, there will be a reflected and refracted beam. This means that both the speed of light and flux, dynamical quantities, are present in the problem and the static probability statement ((1)) may be expressed in terms of dynamic quantities: $\text{Incident flux} / c_1 = \text{Reflected flux} / c_1 + \text{Refracted flux} / c_2 = \text{Incident flux} / p_1 = \text{Reflected flux} / p_1 + \text{Refracted flux} / p_2$. ((2)) (using $E=pc$ with E the same for all cases). There is a catch, however, Flux is an average value in this problem, not an exact one as in Newtonian deterministic dynamics.

In other words, one really has a discrete probability problem because one may have a row of incident photons and the first 10 may reflect, followed by the next 7 refracting etc. The flux picture is an average one which may be applied at the end. As a result, there is no particular problem with using square roots of flux (or other functions of flux) as flux is not the key physical concept in the problem. One is rather trying to describe the probabilistic problem by making use of functions of flux so that flux may appear in a final equation.

We suggest that dynamical variables are, however, key because the probability to reflect is 0 if $p_1=p_2$ or $c_1=c_2$. Thus, we suggest that it is a function of p_1-p_2 . We elaborate on this.

((2)) immediately shows that flux is not conserved, yet there is no source or sink. In fluid dynamics, flux is conserved, i.e. $A_1 v_1 = A_2 v_2$, where A is pipe area and v , speed. Fluid dynamics involves following material in time as does deterministic Newtonian mechanics. How can ((2)) be interpreted? It seems that even though there are dynamic quantities such as c and flux, one does not follow material in time. If one does not follow material in time, then it seems that one has an equilibrium situation, but this is unlike a usual equilibrium because there is flow which would seem to be deterministic, although ((1)) shows that it is probabilistic.

The probabilistic/dynamical picture seems to be a paradox. To try to shed light on it, we consider the reflected flux. This value must become 0 if $c_1=c_2$ or $p_1=p_2$. We suggest defining a variable which demonstrates c_1-c_2 or p_1-p_2 because p and c have the same weight in $E=pc$. This leads to: $(p_1-p_2)/(p_2+p_1)$ which is equivalent to $(c_1-c_2)/(c_1+c_2)$.

We suggest that reflected flux is an even function of this variable. The simplest case is: $\{ (p_1-p_2)/(p_2+p_1) \}^2$. Experimentally, one may check that the reflected flux is the same if one interchanges c_1 and c_2 .

We suggest that it is interesting that for $p_1 > p_2$, (p_1-p_2) becomes smaller (positive) as p_1 becomes closer to p_2 , until it is finally 0. If one considered p_1 becoming less than p_2 , then one would have a negative value. Such a trend could possibly apply to a flux equation: $AA/c_1 - BB/c_1 = CC/c_2$ where AA is incident flux, BB reflected and CC refracted. For this to be the case, one would need to use B which is the square root of flux. In a Newtonian dynamical deterministic problem, one would not take the square root of flux because it is not a physical entity. We have suggested above, however, that one has a probabilistic problem in which one does not follow a particle in time. One does not use flux conservation and so one does not need

to follow matter in time or treat flux as the key quantity in the problem. The notion that reflected flux is an even function of $(p_1-p_2)/(p_1+p_2)$ suggests that the square root of flux may be useful. Furthermore, constant flux is associated with equal probability to have particles at each x . We have argued that this is equivalent to $P(x)=\text{constant} = P_d(p,x)P_d(-p,x)$ or $P_d(p,x) = \exp(ipx)$, i.e. a dynamic probability may exist.

In this note, we wish to focus, however, on the square root of reflected flux as solving the problem and this also leads to quantum mechanical ideas.

Fluid Dynamics Versus Reflection-Refraction.

In classical fluid dynamics, one equates fluxes if one has a large pipe emptying into a smaller one, i.e.

$$A_1 v_1 = A_2 v_2 \quad ((2)) \quad \text{Here } A \text{ is pipe area and } v, \text{ speed.}$$

This approach is dynamical and follows pieces of fluid in time. There is no sink or source so the number of particles which leave the first pipe per second must equal the number of particles which flow in the second pipe per second.

If one has one dimensional reflection-refraction, one may have a row of photons moving in n_1 (index of refraction) to an n_1 - n_2 junction. At the junction, there is a probability for a photon to reflect or refract. As a result, there is a probability for the first ten photons to reflect, the next 20 to refract etc. In other words, one need not have steady flow in time (at least for intervals of time) if one is really watching this problem in time. In particular, the notion of steady flow is an average concept. We suggest that ((2)) is not an average concept.

Thus, one may use the notion of flux which is physical on average in the one-dimensional reflection-refraction problem. One must, however, stress that this flux is an average and that there are actually discrete probabilistic events occurring. One may then write a basic probability statement for reflection-refraction ((1)) as:

$$AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2 \quad ((3)) \quad \text{Here } AA, BB, CC \text{ are the incident, reflected and refracted average fluxes}$$

Thus, it seems that one really wishes to solve a discrete probability problem in terms of average flux. In such a situation, one does not have conservation of flux as seen in ((3)), but this is not a dynamic deterministic problem and so this is not necessarily a concern.

A main point we wish to make is that $BB=0$ if $n_1=n_2$. Here BB is the reflected flux. This suggests that BB is an even function of c_1-c_2 or p_1-p_2 . If one wishes to have a variable which holds for both c and p because $E=pc$, then one may suggest:

$$\text{Variable} = (p_2-p_1) / (p_1+p_2) = (c_2-c_1) / (c_1+c_2) \quad ((4))$$

The simplest even function is to square this variable. We consider this function as an example. We note that from ((3)), $c_1 > c_2$ means that $AA > CC$. This means that B written as $c_2 - c_1$ is negative when $A > C$. When $c_1 = c_2$, $A = C$ and $B = 0$. If one were to continue with $c_2 > c_1$, then B becomes positive. Given that $c_2 > c_1$, this means that CC may increase in ((3)) and it is possible that CC/AA becomes > 1 . In such a case, it seems that B , the square root reflected flux follows a certain trend, i.e. being negative when $AA > CC$ and being positive when $AA < CC$.

To see this more clearly, one may examine actual values of A and B obtained using a traditional matching of electric field and first derivative approach from (1) i.e.

$$B/A = (c_2 - c_1) / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((5a)) \quad \text{and} \quad C/A = 2c_2 / (c_1 + c_2) \quad ((5b))$$

Thus, B may have physical significance in this problem even though it is the square root of reflected flux. In a deterministic Newtonian problem one would not take the square root of flux because it is not a physical quantity, Here, however, one has a probabilistic problem in which flux is an average quantity and is not conserved so one would not necessarily need to be worry about using its square root. One only needs the average equation ((3)) to appear at the end. It is not the full information because it is only an average. Furthermore, it is the dynamical variables p_1 , p_2 which are key because $B=0$ if $p_1 = p_2$. Thus, one may consider finding a functional link between the dynamical variable and flux, in order to describe the dynamical variable in terms of flux, as this is a customary value in Newtonian mechanics.

If B is supposed to have physical meaning, one may try to link it with A and C , i.e. use square root values throughout. In such a case, one may see that these square root flux values follow from ((3)) by using a difference of squares, i.e.

$$A + B = C \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad p_1 A - p_1 B = p_2 C \quad ((6b))$$

Solving ((6a)) and ((6b)) yields ((5a)) and ((5b))

Thus, it seems that one has a consistent result with B being the simplest even function of $(c_2 - c_1) / (c_2 + c_1)$ in the square root approach.

In other notes, we have used the notion of a p - x dynamical probability equal to $\exp(ipx)$ such that ((6a)) is the continuity of sums of this probability and ((6b)), continuity of its first derivative.

Here we focus on the idea of linearizing ((3)) because of the sign switch of B i.e. $c_2 - c_1$.

B as a Bridge Between A and C

In the above sections, it seems that we are considering B as a bridge between A and C . We suggest that the fact that B changes sign, but not magnitude if one interchanges n_1 and n_2 suggests that it is really trying to allow for a kind of match between a structure in A (namely $\exp(ip_1 x)$) and a structure in C , namely $\exp(ip_2 x)$. In the above we noted the symmetry of B

and how it changes sign for $c_2 < c_1$ to $c_1 = c_2$ to $c_2 > c_1$. We suggest that this bridge behaviour of B is linked to creating an equilibrium type of picture even though there is motion in one direction. We call this dynamical equilibrium. The bridge building feature of B is present in the use of the variable $((4))$ which only changes sign on the interchange of 1 and 2.

Why Solve for Fluxes in the First Place?

Given that one dimensional reflection-refraction is probabilistic and is not solved by Newtonian determinism, why should one solve in terms of fluxes in the first place? Fluxes are a well-known and exact concept in classical physics and so if they exist on average in the one dimensional reflection-refraction problem, they serve to show how this problem differs from the classical one. In principle, one could use probabilities of reflection and refraction instead, although fluxes allow for a simpler representation.

More importantly, however, is the fact that one may link flux to dynamic variables such as p (or c). For example, we argue that BB (an average flux linked to probability to reflect) is an even function of $(p_2 - p_1)/(p_1 + p_2)$. This means that probability is described in terms of dynamical variables, i.e. p . In other words, there is something probabilistic about p and its motion in x .

This is key to the problem, we argue, in fact the probability in x is: $\exp(ipx)$, i.e. one deals with a dynamical probability. There is motion in one direction and speeds and momentum also in this direction. These dynamical variables (e.g. p or c) are not only present in deterministic Newtonian mechanics, but also in a probabilistic view. As was seen above, $BB=0$ if $p_1=p_2$ or $c_1=c_2$, i.e. the dynamical conditions have bearing on the probabilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction, studying the reflection probability is key. We argue that it must be zero for $c_1=c_2$ or $p_1=p_2$ or $n_1=n_2$. Thus, we argue that it should be an even function of $c_1 - c_2$ or $p_1 - p_2$. Given that $E=pc$ and p and c appear in the same form, we suggest using a variable which allows one to convert from c to p and yet keeps its form, namely $(p_2 - p_1) / (p_1 + p_2) = (c_2 - c_1) / (c_2 + c_1)$. This function changes sign if $p_2 < p_1$. Even though probability (or flux / c) should be a positive quantity, we suggest that the sign changes of the square root of flux may be relevant to describe $C/A > 1$ or $C/A < 1$. In other words, the math seems to be at the level of a square root of flux and not flux.

A point we stress is that the reflection probability (or average flux/ c) is a function of $p_2 - p_1$, so the dynamical variables p are associated with probability.

In Newtonian mechanics this is not acceptable because flux is an exact quantity. In one dimensional reflection-refraction, however, it is not - it is only an average one. For example, 20 photons may all reflect and then another 7 may refract etc. This is not a smooth picture. Flux is not conserved in this problem and so one does not deal with Newtonian motion. Rather, one has probability which is nevertheless linked to dynamical variables because BB is an even function of $(p_2 - p_1)/(p_2 + p_1)$. We suggest considering square root flux values, e.g. A, B, C . This is easily done using the probability equation $AA/c_1 = BB/c_1 + CC/c_2$ and a difference of squares. One

may then see that B serves a bridge between A and C. We pointed out in a previous note, that $c_1=c_2$, $c_1>c_2$ and $c_2>c_1$ (numbers interchanged) represent quantization of B in a sense.

Reference

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change